

BRACHIAL PLEXOPATHY IN A CASE OF CARCINOMA BREAST: A RARE PRESENTATION

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ABSTRACT Brachial plexopathy in breast cancer patients can be due to two main causes; one being tumour infiltration and other being radiation therapy. In literature, a lot has been written about radiation-induced brachial plexopathy. Primary and secondary tumours of brachial plexus are the most common cause of brachial plexopathy. Plexus neuropathies usually observed in patients with breast cancer at a variable time interval following surgery; cause being recurrence and adjuvant radiotherapy; attributing factor being radiation-induced fibrosis. We are reporting a case of 65 years old lady of carcinoma breast who presented with brachial plexopathy at initial presentation. The purpose of reporting this case is to emphasize significant morbidity produced by the involvement of nerves of brachial plexus in patients with carcinoma breast in the absence of surgery and radiotherapy leading to the diagnostic dilemma, its irreversible nature and its challenging management.

KEYWORDS Brachial plexopathy, Carcinoma breast, Gabapentin.

Introduction

Carcinoma breast is leading cancer worldwide. The study conducted by an international consortium of the researcher, coordinated by Institute of Health Metrics and Evaluation (IHME) at the University of Washington showed breast cancer as top killer among women and lung cancer in men in India. The common sites of breast cancer metastasis are bones, lung, liver and rarely gastrointestinal tract and brachial plexus. The brachial plexus is a somatic plexus formed by intercommunication among the ventral rami of the lower four cervical nerves (C5-C8) and the first thoracic nerve (T1) and is responsible for motor innervations of all the muscles of the upper extremity except the trapezius and levator scapula. Also, it supplies all the cutaneous innervations of the upper limb except for the area of the axilla (which is supplied by the supraclavicular nerve). Brachial plexopathy is a

rare condition and a significant cause of pain and disability in upper limb in carcinoma patients with an incidence of < 0.5%. [1,2,3] Primary tumours of brachial plexus like schwannoma and neurofibromas are generally benign while secondary neoplasms are malignant. The most common causes of brachial plexus involvement are from metastatic breast and lung cancer. [4] In breast cancer, brachial plexopathy can be due to metastasis or radiation-induced fibrosis. Squamous cell carcinoma of head and neck, melanomas, malignant mesotheliomas have a propensity to spread to axillary lymph nodes. Severe pain along the distribution of involved nerves and atrophy of muscles causing weakness in upper extremities are the common presenting symptoms. [5] Contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CECT), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI), Positron Emission Tomography (PET CT) of brachial plexus region along with Nerve Conduction Velocity (NCV) and Electromyography (EMG) helps in establishing the diagnosis. The combined use of analgesics round the clock with aggressive physiotherapy can be a great help to the patient.

Case report

We are reporting a case of 65 years old lady who presented to surgery OPD with complaints of a lump in an upper outer quadrant of left breast for two years and lump in left axilla for

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Figure 1

eight months (Figure 1). She also complained of sharpshooting agonising pain in left forearm and weakness in left hand for past 6 months. It was the pain in the left forearm and hand which brought the patient to the hospital. Pain was disturbing her routine life, sometimes awakening her from sleep. At the time of presentation, patient was unable to use her left hand without support. On examination, there was a hard lump of size 4x4 cm in an upper outer quadrant of the left breast, fixed to underlying structures but free from overlying skin. There was another hard fixed lump of size 4x4 cm in left axilla with associated puckering of overlying skin. Shoulder movements were restricted. There was a reduced sensation in the left upper limb as compared to right upper limb. Muscle wasting was noted in left thenar area (Figure 2). Patient was not able to make a fist in left hand. All routine investigations were normal except increased random blood sugar levels. On further investigations both fasting and postprandial blood sugar levels were deranged. Glycosylated hemoglobin was 9.5. Patient was put on oral hypoglycemic drugs after consultation from physician. FNAC from left breast lump and left axilla revealed infiltrating ductal carcinoma with metastasis to left axillary lymph nodes. The tumour was ER+ve, PR +ve and Her 2 Neu +ve. Mammogram showed Breast Imaging-Reporting and Data System (BI-RADS) VI lesion in breast with thickening of skin and subcutaneous tissue in left axilla. CECT chest revealed heterogeneously enhancing lesion within the left breast involving overlying skin and underlying pectoralis major and serratus anterior muscle with further posterior extension and involvement of left subscapularis muscle. However MRI done for brachial plexus involvement was essentially normal. NCV evaluation showed no response and decreased response in left median nerve and left ulnar motor nerve respectively (Figure 3). Bone scan was normal. Ultrasonography abdomen was normal. This patient did not show any evidence of distant metastasis. She was planned for neoadjuvant chemotherapy as a primary therapy as patient was not willing for any surgical intervention for her problem. Docetaxel and cyclophosphamide-based six cycles of neoadjuvant therapy were given. A good response was observed with chemotherapy, but there was no relief in pain in left forearm and hand. A tumour in left breast and axilla completely disappeared after four cycles of chemotherapy. The patient was kept under follow up and tablet tamoxifen 20mg OD as hormone therapy was given. Tablet metformin for diabetes, capsule methyl cobalamine and gabapentin to take care of neuropathic pain were given. Patient was also asked to follow the physiotherapist instructions.

Figure 2

Figure 3

Discussion

Brachial plexopathy can be caused by inflammation, direct trauma, stretch injuries, pressure from a tumour in the axilla and radiation-induced fibrosis causing thickening of nerves. In our case-patient was having a hard, fixed lump in axilla with puckering of skin over the lump in the axilla. The explanation for the involvement of brachial plexus lies in the fact that one of the significant lymphatic drainages of the breast is through the apex of the axilla. So it is not uncommon for metastatic breast involving brachial plexus. In our case, CECT showed infiltration into subscapularis muscle which is in close relation with brachial plexus that could also explain the involvement of brachial plexus. Restricted left shoulder movement could be explained based on CT findings as subscapularis is the largest and strongest muscle in the rotator cuff and the tumor involved it in our case. Brachial plexus involvement in radiation-induced fibrosis usually presents with sensory deficits. Neurological deficits, the rapid increase in the size of the mass and severe pain at rest which was not relieved by analgesics strongly suggest malignancy as seen in this case. Metastatic lymphadenopathy may encase the neurovascular bundle and result in vascular and neural symptoms. [6] MRI is a good investigation to differentiate between brachial plexopathy due to radiation fibrosis or due to infiltration by tumour cells. [7,8] 18 FDG PET scanning is a useful tool in the evaluation of patients with suspected metastatic plexopathy, particularly if other imaging studies are normal. It may also be useful in distinguishing between radiation-induced and metastatic plexopathy [9]. In our case MRI did not demonstrate the involvement of brachial plexus, so 18 FDG PET would

have been a useful tool, but it was not done due to lack of this facility at our centre and outside cost was not affordable by the patient. The clinical indications for requesting CT of the brachial plexus and axilla include arm oedema, brachial plexus neuropathy and the presence of axillary mass. [10] In our case, we asked for CT to evaluate lump in the left axilla. Median nerve (C5, C6, C7, C8, T1) innervates most of the flexors of the forearm and intrinsic muscles of thumb. It also provides sensory innervations to lateral 3.5 digits. Ulnar nerve innervates intrinsic muscles of the hand and sensory innervations to medial 1.5 fingers. In our case, these two nerves of the left hand were involved, and the patient was having symptoms in their distribution area. To counter the pain caused by brachial plexopathy use of NSAIDs, opioid analgesics, antidepressants like amitriptyline, anticonvulsants like carbamazepine, gabapentin are recommended. Diabetes mellitus is said to be associated with increased symptoms of neuropathic pain, so good control of sugar levels is also mandatory. Gabapentin has a good effect on diabetic patients also. USG guided Pulsed radiofrequency treatment within brachial plexus is a newer technique to relieve pain in pain clinics by the anesthesiologist. [11]

Conclusion

Breast carcinoma patients are presenting with unrelenting pain and weakness of ipsilateral upper limb; brachial plexopathy should be considered as one of the differential diagnosis. Timely diagnosis and intervention can halt the progression of neuropathy. A multidisciplinary team of surgeons, medical oncologists, physiotherapist and anesthesiologist can play a vital role in the management of such patients. Lack of awareness about breast cancer still exists in India especially in a rural setup that is the reason for late reporting of patient and relatively increased morbidity due to advanced disease.

Patient consent

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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